

Bioactive membranes for bone regeneration applications: Effect of physical and biomolecular signals on mesenchymal stem cell behavior

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Abstract

This study focuses on the *in vitro* characterization of bioactive elastin-like recombinamer (ELR) membranes for bone regeneration applications. Four bioactive ELRs exhibiting epitopes designed to promote mesenchymal stem cell adhesion (RGDS), endothelial cell adhesion (REDV), mineralization (HAP), and both cell adhesion and mineralization (HAP-RGDS) were synthesized using standard recombinant protein techniques. The materials were then used to fabricate ELR membranes incorporating a variety of topographical micropatterns including channels, holes and posts. Primary rat mesenchymal stem cells (rMSCs) were cultured on the different membranes and the effects of biomolecular and physical signals on cell adhesion, morphology, proliferation, and differentiation were evaluated. All results were analyzed using a custom-made MATLAB program for high throughput image analysis. Effects on cell morphology were mostly dependent on surface topography, while cell proliferation and cell differentiation were largely dependent on the biomolecular signaling from the ELR membranes. In particular, osteogenic differentiation (evaluated by staining for the osteoblastic marker osterix) was significantly enhanced on cells cultured on HAP membranes. Remarkably, cells growing on membranes containing the HAP sequence in non-osteogenic differentiation media exhibited significant up-regulation of the osteogenic marker as early as day 5, while those growing on fibronectin-coated glass in osteogenic differentiation media did not. These results are part of our ongoing effort to develop an optimized molecularly designed periosteal graft.

Introduction

Alternative therapies that improve bone regeneration, such as more effective bone grafts, continue to be a major necessity in the medical community [1]. The periosteum plays a critical role during bone fracture healing [2], and its incorporation as an active component of the surgical procedure has been demonstrated to significantly enhance bone regeneration [3]. Therefore, engineering periosteal grafts through membrane-based technologies is an attractive approach to improve bone healing [4]. Membranes based on polyesters [5], periosteal cell sheets [6], or even natural proteins [7] have been used towards this goal. For example, platelet-rich fibrin membranes have been used as scaffolds for periosteal tissue engineering [8] and collagen-based membranes have successfully formed a multiple layer-like tissue *in vitro* [7]. Furthermore, some studies have reported that platelet-rich plasma-based [9] or chitosan [10] membranes wrapped around an osteoconductive scaffold enhanced the regeneration of bone defects. Nonetheless, limitations, such as a lack of biocompatibility, early degradation, poor mechanical properties, and a lack of control over bioactivity, have limited the success of periosteal grafts [5].

In an effort to develop more bioactive and tuneable periosteal grafts we have recently reported on several approaches using peptide-based materials [11,12]. Elastin-like recombinamers (ELRs) are genetically engineered protein-based polymers inspired by the

extracellular matrix protein elastin [13]. ELRs are mainly composed of the repeating pentapeptide domain VPGXG, where X could be any amino acid other than proline. Furthermore, ELRs can easily be enriched with functional epitopes designed to elicit a specific biological response, such as cell adhesion [11,14] or biomineralization [15]. Their molecular versatility, biomimetic character, biocompatibility, mechanical properties, and biodegradability [14] are highly attractive elements to incorporate in a periosteal graft strategy.

Biomolecular signaling provided by growth factors, cytokines, and many other proteins and macromolecules plays a key role in the natural process of bone healing. Many short peptide sequences have been identified as potential candidates to enhance therapeutic approaches to bone regeneration [16]. Examples include the well-known cell adhesion sequences RGDS [17] and REDV [14], peptides that nucleate and guide mineralization like DDDEEKFLR-RIGRFG [18] and S(P) [19], or peptides that promote osteogenic cell growth like ALKRQGRTLYGFGG [20]. These and many other bioactive epitopes represent a rich toolbox for the fabrication of bioactive peptide-based scaffolds.

Similarly, it is well established that surface topographical patterns affect, and in many cases control, cell behavior [21]. For example, microposts have been used to study cell adhesion [22], direct cell migration [23], or stimulate proliferation [24], microchannels have been shown to control the morphology and migration of a large variety of cells [25], and microholes have been utilized to enhance cell differentiation [26] and to study cytoskeletal morphology [27]. The incorporation of both biomolecular and physical signaling within membrane scaffolds could significantly enhance the bioactivity and functionality of periosteal grafts. However, while extensive work has been carried out on stimulating cells through either surface topography or bioactive peptides, little is known about their synergistic or competitive effect. Hence we present the *in vitro* validation of bioactive ELR membranes that contain a variety of both surface topographies and bioactive epitopes known to play a role in bone regeneration. The membranes were used as substrates for the culture of primary rat mesenchymal stem cells (rMSCs) and their behavior was quantified in terms of cell adhesion, morphology, proliferation, and differentiation.

Materials and methods

ELR molecules

ELRs were supplied by the BIOFORGE group at the University of Valladolid, Spain. Specifically, the materials consisted of repeating pentapeptide domains of VPGIG and VPGKG, with the amino acid lysine (K) enabling ELR cross-linking, the peptides RGDS and REDV for mesenchymal stem cell and endothelial cell adhesion, respectively, the peptide DDDEEKFLRRIGRFG for nucleation of mineralization (HAP), and an ELR that combined the latter and the RGDS sequence (HAP-RGDS) (Table 1).

Membrane fabrication

Membranes were fabricated according to a recently reported method [11]. Briefly, the fabrication process included: (i) preparation of ELR and cross-linker solutions; (ii) mixing of solutions and the onset of ELR cross-linking; (iii) spin coating of cross-linking ELR; (iv) solvent

evaporation, cross-linked ELR assembly, and membrane release. The ELRs were dissolved in anhydrous dimethylformamide (DMF) (Sigma–Aldrich, Germany) at room temperature, and then mixed with hexamethyl diisocyanate (HDI) (Sigma–Aldrich, Germany). The key parameters used to fabricate the ELR membranes included ELR and cross-linker concentrations, the mould, wettability, cross-linking reaction time, temperature, humidity, and solvent evaporation (Fig. 1a). Five ELR membranes were fabricated from the different ELR molecules, containing either one of the bioactive sequences (RGDS, REDV, HAP, and HAP-RGDS) or without bioactivity (IK).

Fabrication of molds for topographical patterned membranes

Direct write laser lithography (DWL 66, Heidelberg, Germany) was used to fabricate a silicon chrome photomask (Fig. 1b). A (111)-oriented silicon wafer (Siltronix) was coated with an 8 μm thick layer of SU8–10 photoresist (Microchem Corp., USA), soft baked (65 °C for 2 min and 95 °C for 5 min), and then exposed through the silicon chrome photomask (30 mW cm^{-2} for 3.3 s). It was subsequently post-exposure baked (65 °C for 1 min and 95 °C for 5 min) and developed using SU8 developer (Microchem, USA) for 30 s. Topographies were transferred to polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning, USA) using a standard soft lithography process. The PDMS prepolymer was poured on top of the patterned master, degassed under vacuum for 7 min, and then cured at 65 °C for 2 h. The resulting topographically patterned mold was subsequently used to create membranes with the different structural components.

Topographically patterned membranes

A solution of ELR mixed with HDI was prepared and deposited directly on top of the patterned PDMS mold, allowed to air dry for 24 h, released from the mold, and washed thoroughly (Fig. 1c). An array of four 1.5 x 1.5 mm^2 patterned areas was transferred to the ELR membranes. This array consisted of channels that were 7 μm high, 10 μm wide, and separated by 10 μm wide ridges (Channels); holes that were 7 μm deep and either 10 (Holes10) or 40 (Holes40) μm in diameter and separated by 10 μm ; posts that were 7 μm high, 10 μm in diameter, and separated by 10 μm (Posts) (Fig. 1d).

Membrane characterization

Membrane fabrication and pattern reproducibility were analyzed by qualitative observations using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and profilometry (Fig. 1e–h). Membrane biocompatibility and bioactivity assessment as either the effect of biomolecular or topographical signaling on cell morphology was performed by in vitro culture of rMSCs.

Cell culture

rMSCs were extracted and isolated from rat tibia and fe6mur bone marrow. The bones were provided by the Animal Research Center (PRAAL) of the Parc Científic Barcelona, Spain. Cells were expanded in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) (Life Technologies, Spain) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Attendbio Research, Spain), 1% glutamine (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain), and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain).

rMSCs at passage 3–6 were diluted in serum-free DMEM and seeded onto the substrates at $10,500 \text{ cells cm}^{-2}$. After 2 h culture all the medium was replaced with DMEM containing 10% FBS for subsequent culture. The osteogenic differentiation medium used was prepared with the culture medium described above enriched with 50 mM ascorbic acid, 10 mM sodium β -glycerophosphate and 10^{-8} M dexamethasone (all Sigma–Aldrich, Spain).

Cell culture substrate preparation

The glass (VWR, Spain) and PDMS substrates were sterilized with 70% ethanol, washed with PBS, and then incubated with $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ fibronectin (FN) (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain) solution for 30 min. The glass (Glass-FN) and PDMS substrates were used as controls. ELR membranes (IK, RGDS, REDV, HAP, and HAP-RGDS) were then sterilized by UV irradiation for 10 min on each side and placed in a sterile 24-well plate (VWR, Spain). To ensure cell growth within the patterned areas and to allow for quantitative analysis a PDMS slab containing a 7 mm diameter hole was positioned on each substrate prior to cell inoculation.

Cell fluorescence labeling

Quantification of cell morphology, adhesion and proliferation. In order to quantify the cell morphology, adhesion and proliferation cells were stained to observe the actin cytoskeleton and nuclei as previously reported [28]. After 2 h and 2 and 5 days samples were washed twice with PBS to remove any non-adherent cells. The adherent cells were then fixed with 4% (w/v) paraformaldehyde (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain) in PBS for 30 min and permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain) for 5 min. Cells were then incubated with $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ RNase solution (Roche, Spain) for 20 min. After three washes with PBS the cells were stained with phalloidin–fluorescein isothiocyanate (phalloidin–FITC) (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain) at 1:50 dilution in PBS for 30 min at room temperature in order to observe the actin cytoskeleton. In addition, the cells were counterstained with DRAQ5 (Biostatus Ltd, UK) at 1:400 dilution in PBS for 10 min at room temperature, in order to visualize their nuclei. Finally, a drop of Fluoro-Gel mountant (Aname, Spain) was placed on the samples, which were immediately positioned cell side down onto a glass slide.

Quantification of cell differentiation. The transcription factor osterix was used to identify and quantify differentiated cells [29]. After 5 days in culture the samples were washed twice with PBS to remove any non-adherent cells. Cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 30 min and then permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 for 10 min. Cells were incubated with $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ RNase solution (Roche, Spain) for 20 min. After three washes with PBS the cells were incubated with a 5% (w/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma–Aldrich, Spain) solution for 1 h to block non-specific protein binding. Cells were incubated with the primary antibody rabbit anti-osterix (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Santa Cruz, CA) diluted to 1:250 in 1% BSA (w/v) in PBS for 1 h. After washing three times with PBS the cells were incubated with a secondary antibody (Alexa Fluor 568-conjugated anti-rabbit IgG, Invitrogen, Spain) diluted to 1:250 in 1% BSA (w/v) in PBS for 1 h. The cells were washed three times with PBS and then stained with phalloidin–FITC and DRAQ5, for visualization of the actin cytoskeleton and nuclei, respectively. The samples were then mounted on glass slides with Fluoro-Gel mountant (Aname, Spain). All steps were carried out at room temperature.

Confocal imaging, image processing, and quantification

Cells cultured on each combination of ELR material and topography as well as the corresponding controls were imaged using a Leica TCS-SP5 confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) equipped with a 10x (NA = 0.4) objective. Each pattern was acquired as a single z-stack using a voxel size of 0.7568 x 0.7568 x 1.2910 μm . All z-stack images were first pre-processed using median filtering, a rolling ball algorithm to remove the background and a 2nd maximum projection to obtain a single image per topography and membrane. Each single image was then used to quantify cell morphology, adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation. For cell morphology 10 cells were randomly chosen from each image and their perimeters were outlined and saved to the Fiji/Image J software (<http://fiji.sc/>) ROI manager tool. The parameters analyzed for each cell were: (1) cell area defined as the area of selection in μm^2 ; (2) cell perimeter defined as the length of the outside boundary of the selection in μm ; (3) cell elongation or aspect ratio (AR) defined as the ratio between the major and minor axes of the ellipse (each cell was fitted to an ellipse). To quantify cell adhesion and proliferation each single image was imported into a custom-made MATLAB program used to quantify the number of cells in a high content mean. Fiji/Image J software was used to quantify differentiation. The number of nuclei stained with osterix was divided by the number of nuclei stained with DRAQ5 in order to obtain the percentage differentiated cells.

SEM sample preparation

SEM observations were used to qualitatively assess membrane fabrication and pattern reproducibility. The substrates were immersed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde (Electron Microscopy Science, USA) in phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (PB) for 1 h and then washed three times with PB. Dehydration was performed by immersing the substrates in increasing concentrations of ethanol in MilliQ water for 10 min each (50%, 70%, 90%, 96% and 100%). The ethanol was then removed while preserving the membrane using critical point drying.

Statistical analysis

All quantitative results are presented as means \pm standard deviations. The data were evaluated using ANOVA and Tukey's test for simultaneous paired comparisons, with the significance level set at the 95% confidence interval ($p < 0.05$). Each experiment consisted of three replicates and was repeated twice.

Results and discussion

Membrane fabrication and characterization

SEM and profilometry qualitatively confirmed topographical patterns with well-defined features that closely resembled those of the PDMS moulds (Fig. 1e–h), with no observable variations between different ELR membranes. While the fabrication technique used in this study has been previously reported [11], a number of fabrication/material developments are here described. First, five different ELR materials were used, including IK, RGDS, REDV, HAP, and HAP-RGDS, each providing a different bioactivity (Table 1). Second, all these materials were

fabricated with new surface topographical features (Channels, Posts, Holes40, Holes10, and Smooth). Finally, the fabrication technique enabled the integration of multiple distinct areas, each one exhibiting different topographical features, within the same membrane (ELR material), minimizing potential variations between the materials and processing batches.

Cell morphology, adhesion, and proliferation

Cell behavior was found to differ depending on the type of membrane and was highly dependent on the type of topography (Fig. 2a). As expected, rMSCs growing on Channels adopted an elongated morphology as early as 2 h after seeding (Fig. 2b and Supplementary data Table S1). On day 2 rMSCs exhibited larger areas and longer perimeters on Smooth membranes (Fig. 2f), independent of the type of material, compared with cells growing on all other substrates, except on the positive control Glass-FN (Supplementary data Table S2). These results are consistent with previous studies describing cell alignment on channels and more spread morphologies on smooth surfaces [25]. On Posts at day 2 (Fig. 2c) cells appeared to spread both over and between the posts, with their lamellopodia surrounding them. Cells cultured on Holes10 (Fig. 2d) and Holes40 (Fig. 2e) seemed to recognize the edge of the hole and, additionally, cells cultured on Holes40 were observed to spread both over and inside the holes. These morphological traits are consistent with previous studies [24,25,30].

Cell adhesion and proliferation were quantified by counting the number of nuclei that were positively stained with DRAQ5 (Supplementary data Table S3). Cells adhered similarly to all Smooth ELR membranes, with expectedly lower adhesion on the negative control PDMS substrates (65 ± 17 cells mm^{-2}) and higher adhesion on the Glass-FN substrates (336 ± 51 cells mm^{-2}). No significant enhancement of or detrimental effect on cell adhesion was observed upon addition of the topographical patterns, except for an increase in cell adhesion on Holes10 REDV membranes (288 ± 63 cells mm^{-2}) (Fig. 3a). While it is well established that the addition of some surface microtopography can enhance cell adhesion [24,31], it is unclear why cells seemed to initially preferentially adhere to this particular substrate after 2 h. The peptide REDV has been linked to endothelial cell adhesion [32], but to our knowledge no effect on MSC adhesion has been reported. It is also unclear why cells did not seem to preferentially adhere to membranes containing the RGDS sequence [33]. However, this is consistent with our previous results reporting that, although exhibiting much clearer focal adhesion in the presence of ELRs with RGDS, cells seemed to adhere in similar numbers to ELRs with and without the RGDS sequence [13]. It is also known that cells may be able to selectively recognize and adhere to regions of tropoelastin [34], elastin [35], or elastin-derived peptides (VAPG) [36], which may explain the observed ELR affinity.

With respect to cell proliferation, specific combinations of material/topography exhibited higher cell numbers at various time points. For example, Holes40 IK (536 ± 52 cells mm^{-2}) and Holes10 RGDS (598 ± 285 cells mm^{-2}) membranes exhibited significantly higher numbers of cells on day 2 (Fig. 3b), while Holes10 IK (960 ± 84 cells mm^{-2}) and Posts REDV (802 ± 18 cells mm^{-2}) membranes contained more cells on day 5 (Fig. 3c). However, a clear trend was observed for the HAP membranes. On day 2 the HAP membranes (independent of

the topography) contained the lowest number of cells of all membranes tested, ranging from 159 ± 33 on Holes40 to 243 ± 90 cells mm^{-2} on Channels. However, by day 5 cells growing on the same HAP membranes had increased their proliferation, resulting in a similar quantity of cells to the other membranes, extending from 736 ± 201 on Posts to 966 ± 206 cells mm^{-2} on Holes10. This distinctive proliferation effect observed on all HAP membranes may be related to the observed enhanced differentiation described below.

Cell differentiation

In this study cell differentiation was investigated by analyzing the translocation of osterix to the nuclei of rMSCs on day 5. Osterix is a transcription factor required for early stage differentiation of preosteoblasts into fully functioning osteoblasts [29]. Its expression has been correlated with increases in bone marrow stem cell proliferation, alkaline phosphatase activity, and mineralization in vitro [37,38]. Immunofluorescence staining of osterix facilitated the observation of individual differentiating cells and, consequently, their quantification by counting the number of individual nuclei (Fig. 4a). This technique enabled the use of ELR membranes with surfaces comprising all of the different topographical patterns within the same membrane and helped minimize potential variations between types of materials. Cell differentiation was investigated on day 5 in order to better identify the effect of the two main variables (material and topography), while minimizing possible effects related to cell–cell communication or culture confluence. Furthermore, analysis of cell differentiation on day 5 allowed a better evaluation of the effect of the membranes on cell differentiation prior to the natural expression of osterix by differentiating cells on day 7 [29].

Interestingly, differentiation of cells growing on both HAP (Fig. 4b) and HAP-RGDS (Fig. 4c) membranes was significantly affected, with higher numbers of differentiated cells on HAP membranes on day 5. These membranes exhibited the highest numbers of osterix-expressing cells compared with other substrates, such as PDMS Smooth (Fig. 4e), including the positive control Glass-FN (Fig. 4d). All HAP membranes contained differentiating cells, ranging between 12 ± 20 (Posts) and 31 ± 25 (Channels) of cells expressing osterix on day 5, without the use of osteogenic differentiation medium (Supplementary data Table S4). Remarkably, at this early time point not even the cells growing on Glass-FN in osteogenic differentiation medium expressed the protein osterix. These results demonstrate a strong early stage osteogenic stimulation of rMSCs when cultured on the HAP material, independent of the topography.

The bioactive epitope present in the HAP ELR material sequence (DDDEEKFLRRIGRFG) corresponds to the SNA15 and SN15 fragments of statherin, a protein found in saliva that is known to have an affinity for hydroxyapatite [39] and participates in the nucleation and/or growth of calcium phosphate minerals [40]. Our results demonstrate a significant enhancement of early stage osteoblastic differentiation of rMSCs growing on HAP and HAP-RGDS membranes, as evident as sound osterix expression, even in the absence of osteogenic differentiation medium. Both of these membranes were fabricated using the same amount of ELR by weight. However, the number of HAP epitopes in the HAP recombinamer ($0.283 \mu\text{mol}$ per membrane) is higher than the number existing in the HAP-RGDS

recombinamer (0.148 μmol per membrane) for the same weight. Consequently, this differentiation stimulus seemed to be related to the number of bioactive epitopes present in the membrane, which would explain the higher number of differentiated cells observed on HAP (where more signaling molecules would be present) compared with HAP-RGDS. Nonetheless, the specific mechanism by which the bioactive epitope present on HAP-containing membranes stimulates osteoblastic differentiation is not yet understood.

To our knowledge direct epitope-mediated stimulation of osteogenic differentiation through presentation of the statherin fragment DDDEEKFLRRIGRFG has not been reported. An alternative explanation for the enhanced cell differentiation observed on all HAP membranes may be found in a biophysical process related to the hydroxyapatite affinity of the statherin fragment. It has been reported that calcium phosphate can have an osteoinductive effect on MSCs [41]. Furthermore, osteoblastic differentiation has been shown to be enhanced on surfaces with relatively high stiffness [42]. From these observations an intriguing possibility is that cells growing on HAP membranes were exposed to earlier nucleated calcium phosphate material on the membranes, which may subsequently have increased the stiffness that the cells sensed. In either case, stimulation of osteoblastic differentiation by a peptide inducing mineralization is an interesting possibility that would require further study.

While no significant differences were observed between the different surface topographies with respect to differentiation on day 5, it is important to take into account a variety of factors. First, although there seemed to consistently be more osterix-expressing cells on HAP and HAP-RGDS Channels than on any other substrate, the difference was not statistically significant. However, the inherent variability of primary rMSCs may have limited identification of this possibility [43]. Interestingly, cells on these two membranes exhibited the highest areas of all other membranes with channel topographies at 2 h, suggesting a possible synergistic effect of the channel topography and HAP on morphology, proliferation, and differentiation. Second, it is possible that the strong differentiating effect provided by the HAP membranes may have begun as early as day 2, when cell proliferation was seen to significantly decrease on HAP-containing membranes. It is well known that an increase in cell differentiation can lead to a decrease in proliferation [44]. In addition, it has been demonstrated that osterix can increase both proliferation and osteoblastic differentiation [37], which in our case would explain the increased proliferation observed between days 2 and 5. This strong early stage effect of the HAP material may be affecting or masking potential topographic effects on cell differentiation. Furthermore, it is plausible that a possible differentiation effect due to surface topography may only be observable at later time points. For example, enhanced osteoblastic differentiation on substrates comprising similar 10 μm diameter posts [45] and 40 μm diameter holes [30] has been reported on day 9 using PDMS and day 7 using peptide amphiphiles.

Third, given the well-known dependence of surface topographical effects on cell type [46], material properties [47], and microtopography geometry [48], it is possible that shape variations in the current topographies may significantly increase the effect on cell differentiation or other cell responses. Finally, another alternative is the possibility that a synergistic effect of surface topography and biochemical signaling may be magnified when

using topographical features one order of size below, down to the nanoscale. For example, it has been reported that nanotopographies resulted in the highest expression levels of two important osteogenic marker genes and bone mineral formation compared with microtopographies [49], and also how the combined effect of nanofibre topography with sustained biochemical signaling enhanced MSC neuronal differentiation [50]. In this situation the effect of nanotopography may go beyond their direct cellular interaction and also influence the presentation and bioactivity of the biochemical elements. However, it is important to bear in mind that although previous studies have used a single osteoblastic stain to analyze cell differentiation [51,52], validation of these hypotheses would require a more in-depth examination of the observed osteoblastic differentiation on HAP membranes. In addition, studies should also be conducted using human MSCs, as variations in cell differentiation between species are well established [53]. Nonetheless, the diverse focus of our study in identifying multiple topographical, biochemical, and their combined effects on cell adhesion, morphology, proliferation, and differentiation has permitted the identification of key effects which we hope to further explore in more detail.

Conclusion

Membranes exhibiting selective and tuneable bioactivity capable of eliciting specific biological responses may offer a more efficient periosteal graft alternative improving bone regeneration. Herein we report a systematic investigation of the effects of ELR membranes with a variety of bioactive epitopes and/or surface topographies. Membranes were fabricated and characterized to verify reproducibility and lithography precision. While some differences were noticed at different time points, no major trends were observed with regards to initial cell adhesion and morphology. However, rMSC proliferation was clearly affected on all HAP membranes, initially slowing down their growth from day 0 to 2, but then significantly increasing it by day 5. Most importantly, early expression of the osteoblastic transcription factor osterix was strongly induced in cells growing on HAP membranes, and to a lesser degree on HAP-RGDS membranes, independent of topography. Strong expression of this osteoblastic marker was seen on day 5 in up to 31% of cells growing on HAP membranes, while no expression was observed in cells growing in all other membranes. Remarkably, this osteoblastic differentiation was observed on day 5 using a non-osteogenic differentiation medium, whereas cells on all other substrates, including those on the positive control Glass-FN growing in osteogenic differentiation medium, did not express osterix. This study has helped to identify a biomolecular signal that can be incorporated into ELR membranes and is part of our ongoing effort to develop a periosteal graft for enhanced bone regeneration.

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Table 1
Sequence and functionality (bioactivity) of the elastin-like recombinamer (ELR) materials.

ELR Material	ELR sequence (bioactive sequence)	Bioactivity
IK	$(VPGIG\ VPGIG\ VPGKG\ VPGIG\ VPGIG)_{24}$	Control
RGDS	$[[[(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_2AVTGRGDSPASS[(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_6]$	Cell Adhesion
HAP	$[[[(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_2\ DDDEEKFLRRIGRFG\ [(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_3]$	Mineralization
HAP-RGDS	$[[[(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_2\ DDDEEKFLRRIGRFG\ [(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_4][[(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_4AVTGRGDSPASS\ [(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}]_4]$	Mineralization and cell adhesion
REDV	$((VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}EEIQIGHIPREDVDYHLYP(VPGIG)_2(VPGKG)(VPGIG)_{2,2}(VGVAPG)_3)_{10}$	Cell Adhesion

Fig. 1. (a) Key parameters used to fabricate the ELR membranes. (b) Silicon chrome photomask used to transfer the four different geometrical patterns onto (c) single ELR membranes. (d) Geometries and dimensions of the designed topographical patterns. SEM and optical profilometry (inset) images of (e) channels, (f) holes40, (g) posts, and (h) holes10 on ELR membranes used to qualitatively validate the fabrication process [11].

Fig. 2. Morphology of rMSCs growing on membranes made from the different ELR materials and exhibiting the different surface topographies. (a) Comparative summary of representative morphological differences in rMSCs after 2 h (red) and 2 days (blue) growing on the different membranes. Confocal microscopy images of the actin cytoskeleton (green) and nuclei (blue) of representative groups of cells cultured on (b) channels, (c) posts, (d) holes10, (e) holes40 and (f) smooth surfaces on day 2.

Fig. 3. Cell adhesion and proliferation as measured by cell number at (a) 2 h, (b) 2 days, and (c) 5 days on the different ELR material/topography combinations.

Fig. 4. Osteoblastic differentiation as measured by expression of the transcription factor ostein in the nuclei of rMSCs. (a) Percentage of cells growing without osteogenic medium expressing ostein on the different membranes on day 5. The results for cells growing in osteogenic medium on the positive control glass-FN are also presented. Confocal microscopy images of representative regions of the different membranes with ostein-expressing cell nuclei (pink) and non-ostein-expressing cell nuclei (blue) on (b) HAP smooth, (c) HAP channel, (d) glass-FN, and (e) PDMS smooth.